

Megasporocarps and microsporocarps were handpicked, mixed at a 1:2 ratio, and sterilized for spore germination under *in vitro* conditions.

Spores were centrally placed in petri dishes containing sterile NO₃ solid medium. We added 2-3 ml of vitamins (ascorbic acid, vitamin B1, pantothenic acid, nicotinic acid, and riboflavin, each at 25 ppm) and incubated the plates under 1500-2000 lux light.

All vitamins tested stimulated megaspore germination (Table 1). Germination and fertilization were higher with nicotinic acid and riboflavin.

In a survival study, dried sporocarps that had been stored in burlap bags for 1, 2, and 3 yr were presoaked separately for 12 h in growth regulator GA₃ and systemic fungicide carbendazim (both at 100 ppm). These were released into soil extract medium. Another batch of sporocarps was presoaked in a combined solution before release.

Some sporelings developed from all three storage groups (Table 2). Spores stored for 1 yr survived better than older spores, regardless of the soaking solution. Spores from treated sporocarps had improved germination. □

Table 1. Effect of vitamins on *A. microphylla* spore fertilization.

Vitamins (25 ppm)	Fertilization (% emerged sporelings)	Increase (%) over control
Ascorbic acid	49.68	38.19
Vitamin B1	54.46	51.49
Pantothenic acid	56.88	58.22
Nicotinic acid	65.96	83.48
Riboflavin	63.75	77.33
Control	35.95	
CV	24.01	

Table 2. Studies on the viability of frond-based spore inoculum of *A. microphylla* stored in burlap bags.

Presoaking solution (100 ppm)	Sporelings that emerged ^a (no./tub)		
	1 yr old	2 yr old	3 yr old
GA ₃	217.50	13.50	-
Carbendazim	75.50	19.00	2.50
GA ₃ + carbendazim	220.50	3.50	0.50
Control	146.00	7.00	2.50
CV	12.21		

^aEach 5-g dried spore inoculum used 300 megasporocarps. This was constant for each treatment tested.

Use of rice straw under submerged conditions

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We studied the feasibility of applying fresh rice straw under submerged conditions to rice variety Jaya during the 1983 kharif (monsoon) and 1984 wet season (WS).

Soil was loamy with pH 7.8, 0.43% organic C. Available NPK were 181, 6.6, and 152 kg/ha. We incorporated 5 and 10 t straw with and without additional N. A uniform dressing of 26 kg P and 49 kg

K/ha was applied. Straw was incorporated 21 d before transplanting.

Grain and straw yields increased significantly with rice straw incorporation (Table 1). Yield and N uptake were best with 5 t rice straw and 100 kg N/ha applied together.

We examined N mineralization rate in normal (pH 7.8) and sodic (pH 10.1) soils under submerged conditions in the laboratory. Ammoniacal N content was less in sodic than in normal soil (Table 2). This was related to soil organic C content.

In both soils, N content increased up to 30 d, then decreased. Adding rice straw accelerated the mineralization rate. Maximum NH₄-N content (53.5 ppm) was with 200 ppm fertilizer N and 10 t rice straw/ha. □

Table 1. Effect of N fertilizer and rice straw on yield and N uptake by rice plants.

Treatment	1983				1984			
	Yield (t/ha)		N uptake (kg/ha)		Yield (t/ha)		N uptake (kg/ha)	
	Grain	Straw	Grain	Straw	Grain	Straw	Grain	Straw
Control	2.3	4.6	36.7	28.2	2.5	4.2	33.1	25.6
5 t rice straw	3.3	5.7	43.3	35.1	3.0	4.8	39.7	29.9
10 t rice straw	3.3	5.8	44.0	36.6	3.1	5.0	41.0	31.6
100 kg N (urea)	4.1	7.1	55.3	46.6	3.8	6.4	51.2	41.6
100 kg N (urea) + 5 t rice straw	4.4	7.6	59.6	50.2	4.1	7.0	55.7	46.2
100 kg N (urea) + 10 t rice straw	4.4	7.7	60.0	50.6	4.1	7.1	56.1	46.9
LSD (0.05)	0.2	0.4	3.0	2.8	0.2	0.4	2.6	2.5

Table 2. Effect of rice straw on NH₄-N release under submerged condition in normal and sodic soils.

Treatment	NH ₄ -N (ppm)							
	Normal soil				Sodic soil			
	15 d	30 d	45 d	60 d	15 d	30 d	45 d	60 d
Control	10.8	12.1	9.1	5.2	8.0	9.4	5.3	3.0
Rice straw (10 t/ha)	13.7	14.0	9.8	5.6	11.1	13.7	7.6	3.7
Fertilizer N (200 ppm)	38.0	43.3	28.4	11.1	13.7	26.4	15.4	5.7
Fertilizer N (200 ppm) + rice straw (10 t/ha)	45.8	53.5	35.0	12.6	26.6	31.2	18.8	6.1
Mean	27.07	30.72	20.57	8.62	17.35	20.17	11.77	4.62

Integrated pest management—diseases

Managing rice sheath blight (ShB) using fungal antagonists and organic amendments

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We evaluated the efficacy of two antagonistic fungi (*Trichoderma longibrachiatum* [Tl] and *Gliocladium virens* [Gv]) and two organic manures (*Gliricidia maculata* leaves and *Azadirachta indica* [neem] cake), both individually and combined, to control ShB caused by *Rhizoctonia solani*.

Experimental plots (1 m²) were arranged in a randomized block design with three replications at the Madras University Field Research Laboratory, Maduravoyal, Tamil Nadu, during monsoon 1989 and wet season 1989-90. The clay soil had 7.3 pH and 42% water-holding capacity.

Plots were artificially infected with *R. solani*. We incorporated the antagonists and amendments into the soil as a wheat bran/sawdust preparation at 0.5 g/kg soil.

Highly ShB-susceptible TKM9 seeds were direct sown after incubating for 1 wk. Overcrowded seedlings were thinned at 20 d to get approximately 20 x 20-cm spacing. Urea, super-

phosphate, and muriate of potash were split-applied to maintain the NPK level (100-50-50 kg/ha).

Disease incidence was scored using the *Standard evaluation system for rice* (SES).

Both antagonists and amendments—alone and together—significantly decreased ShB intensity and increased grain yield (see table). Amendments protected plants better than antagonists: gliricidia was the best, yielding 42% protection over the control. System integration helped both antagonists to more effectively control ShB.

Gliricidia + Gv increased grain yield the most. There was little variation in straw yield. □

Effect of fungal antagonists and organic amendments on rice yield and ShB intensity in Maduravoyal, Tamil Nadu, India.^a

Treatment	Grain yield (t/ha)	Straw yield (/tha)	Disease incidence (%)	Protection (%) over control
Control	3.0 f	5.3 bc	15.11 a	-
Gliricidia	3.6 ef	5.5 abc	8.71 b	42.4
N neem	4.6 bcd	5.4 bc	8.99 b	40.5
<i>G. virens</i> (Gv)	3.9 de	5.2 c	9.27 b	38.6
<i>T. longirachiatum</i> (Tl)	4.4 cde	5.0 c	9.47 b	37.3
Gliricidia + Gv	5.9 a	6.2 a	7.4 b	49.4
Gliricidia + Tl	5.7 a	5.8 ab	6.66 b	55.9
N neem + Gv	5.4 ab	5.6 abc	8.15 b	46.1
N neem + Tl	5.3 abc	5.5 abc	7.29 b	51.8

^aValues followed by the same letters are not significantly different (p = 0.01) by Duncan's multiple range test.

Detecting and purifying noncapsid protein in rice infected with grassy stunt virus (RGSV)

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RGSV is classified as a tenuivirus. This virus group produces noncapsid protein (NCP), but evidence that RGSV produces NCP is lacking.

We detect NCP in RGSV-infected rice leaves—but not in healthy ones—by using sodium-dodecyl sulfate polyacrylamide gel electrophoresis (SDS-PAGE) Fig. 1). We purified NCP by solubilizing and crystallizing it at differential pH in a citrate phosphate buffer and finally by ultracentrifuging.

NCP dissolved at a pH greater than 7.0 and recrystallized at a pH lower than

6.0. It occurred as needle-shaped crystals as reported in maize stripe, rice stripe, and other tenuiviruses. We obtained many needle-shaped crystals 1.8-9.6 μm long and 0.04-0.4 μm wide in purified extracts from RGSV-infected leaves (Fig. 2).

NCP has a single protein with a molecular weight (MW) of 24 kDa and its coat protein has a MW of 37 kDa (Fig. 1). The purified NCP had a typical protein absorption spectrum with maximum absorbance at 278, minimum absorbance at 252, and 0.6 absorbance ratio (A_{260/280}).

We obtained a yield of about 20 mg/100 g tissue. The NCP of RGSV was very similar to what other tenuiviruses produce, except that it has a slightly higher molecular weight and lower solubility in low-ionic-strength buffer at pH 7.0. □

1. SDS (12%) polyacrylamide slab gel showing A) marker protein, B) 37kDa coat protein (CP) C) 24 kDa noncapsid protein (NCP), D) extracts from RGSV infected rice leaves, and E) healthy rice leaves.

2. Purified noncapsid protein showing needle-like crystals under phase contrast microscopy.

Estimation of rice bacterial sheath brown rot (BSR) and rice blast (BI) severity in five Burundi highland swamps

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Highland swamps (1,200-2,000 m elevation) represent 10% of Burundi's arable land. Rice (Yunnan 3) is grown during the rainy season. BSR, caused by *Pseudomonas fuscovaginae*, and BI, caused by *Pyricularia grisea* are two